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Improving The Students' Reading Comprehension Using Rare (Review, Answer, Read, Express) At SMP Labuhan Deli

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Abstract

This study aims to see whether the RARE strategy can improve students' reading comprehension at SMPN 2 Palibelo. This research is a class action research (CAR). The data obtained in the form of quantitative and qualitative methods. The instrument used by the researcher was in the form of a test (posttest) in the form of multiple choices. There are four steps to doing: planning, acting, observing, and reflecting. This classroom action research was carried out in two cycles. The first cycle was conducted in two meetings and the second cycle in two meetings. The first cycle was carried out by providing material about the types of vehicles and their existence, in the first cycle there was no increase and it was continued in the second cycle, namely with lots and lots of material, and some several. The results of this study indicate that there is an increase in students' reading in cycle II. Researcher found a significant increase in cycle II, this can be seen from the average cycle of 46 for pretest, 62.3 for post-test I and 83 for post test II. So teaching using the RARE strategy shows students are active and enthusiastic in learning English. In addition to the explanation above, the RARE strategy also has several advantages, such as: easy to understand and easy to implement. From the explanation above, the use of the RARE strategy in the learning process of reading comprehension has a positive effect on student achievement, because students can learn easily and relaxed without any burden. I hope this RARE strategy helps more students to improve their reading comprehension.

Keywords: *Rare (Review, Answer, Read, Express), CAR (Classroom Action Research)*

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INTRODUCTION

English is generally considered a language of communication, therefore a person is expected to be able to speak more than one language. This is a language of communication for students, therefore it has many forms, each form is correct and appropriate to the context. The same thing also happens to the learning structure in this country. In fact, it is the only foreign language included in studied. In reality : students find it difficult to understand what they read, deciding procedure in comprehension as well as choosing appropriate media.

There for the writer would like to answer the following question : What things need to be considered to be able to read effectively?. Tips for reading : Set targets, Book preview, Don't read every word. Within 2 months the researcher made observations in class VII, which was used by researchers to see how far their reading comprehension was, especially in English reading comprehension. In the first week the researcher conducted the first phase of observation, namely by looking at how the class was in carrying out teaching and learning activities, especially in English lessons.

Topic controlling idea. English subjects are included in the local content component. That is, the school has the authority to hold English learning or not. According to Tarigan (1998:7) reading is a process which is used by reader in order to get the purpose of the writer through the written word.

reading comprehension, in the second week the researcher was more broad in providing teaching materials to student . After that in the third week the researchers began to give assignments to see the extent of their understanding of the material provided by the researchers. In the third week the researcher gave an assignment then in the next week, from the results of the assignment the researcher got what problems were found to student.

In teaching and learning process, there are some problem, when the researcher did observation to student the researcher found that the lack of reading comprehension especially English to student grade. Thus, students not easily understand English lessons, especially in the field of reading with a challenging text, fluent readers apply these skills consciously and strategically in order comprehend. That teaching reading comprehension to students should be more enthusiastic in learning English,

1. students should focus on learning and mastering basic word understanding skills
2. with regard to rare strategies,
3. And students should focus on the meaning of the text in the reader's memory.

Based on the description above RARE strategy, the researcher able to know the problem to student that it is difficult for students to read and understand English lessons, especially in reading comprehension. the reason why researchers use CAR is because CAR is related to RARE and previous research, and where previous research on RARE is little.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research design used in this study will be Classroom Action Research (CAR). There were some definitions of action research proposed by experts. Carr and Kemmis (1982) in Burns (1999:30) state that action research is simply a form of self-reflective enquiry undertaken by participants in social situation in order to improve the rationality and justice of their own practices, their understanding of this practices and the situations in which the practices are carried out. Researchers use CAR because it relates to the RARE method used by researchers, besides the reason for using CAR is to make it easier to take during research. In this study, the researchers were English teachers, where the researchers taught English using the

Rare Strategy in reading comprehension:

Rare strategy and the subject teachers were observers who observed the teaching and learning process with observation sheets to help researchers collect qualitative data. This Research was conducted at SMP Labuhan Deli class VIII. This study used collaborative research, and student test results were carried out in two cycles because the first cycle was not successful or had not yet reached the KKM. In PTK a researcher can reach the KKM standard in the second cycle and the researcher must stop doing research. Research design is important in research because it makes it easier for researcher to improve the quality of the research do. The design of this research is associative by using a quantitative and qualitative. The research subjects were carried out in grade 2 students of SMP Labuhan Deli in the 203 /2024 academic year with a total of 30 students. The object of this research was teacher, researcher, and students in second grade at SMP Labuhan Deli . Where the researcher use CAR (Classroom Action Research).

Purpose of pretest

According to Riyanto (2010:96) "observation is a data collection method that uses direct and indirect observations". Pre-test is a series or a test or exam given to students at the beginning of learning or certain activities. The purpose of the pretest is to determine the initial ability of students regarding the material to be delivered. The treatment is to provide the subject matter using a strategy RARE after the pre-test is done. Post-test is a series or a test or exam given to students after a material or action has been taught. The purpose of the post test is to determine.

In collecting data, the researcher conducted a pre-test by giving 20 multiple choice questions. after that the researcher will do the treatment by teaching using RARE method , after that to see whether this RARE method is successful or not the author does a post-test cycle I and cycle II to find out if this RARE method is successful or not

Quantitative data

The study applied the quantitative and qualitative data. Quantitative data was used to analyze the score of students while the qualitative data was used to describe the situation during on the teaching process. By applying this data, it was assumed to get the satisfying result of the improving ability in reading comprehension through RARE. The qualitative data was analyzed from the instrument. The quantitative data was analyzed to see the improving of students reading comprehension ability. The writer searched the mean of each posttest every cycle.

Then, after getting mean of students' score per actions' the writer identifies whether or not there might have students' improvement score on reading comprehension from pre-test and post-test

score in cycle I and cycle II.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Findings In this part of the study, the researcher presented the results of the research that had been conducted with class VIII students of SMP Labuhan Deli during four meetings a month from 20 June to 26 July 2024, where the researcher conducted a pre-test on 6 June with the aim of knowing the extent to which reading ability in class VIII has increased and the results of the pre-test show that reading ability in class VIII is still very low, then the researcher conducts the teaching process. on July 7 and 12, after carrying out the teaching process then giving the posttest I on July 14 where to find out whether there has been an increase in the researcher's reading, after the researcher carried out the teaching process, the results of the posttest -test I showed that there was a slight increase compared to the results pre-test, after which the results were then continued to teach again July 22 and 21, where this time the researcher used the RARE strategy for teaching.

RARE strategy for teaching which aims to improve the reading ability of class VIII students, after the teaching process was carried out, then a posttest II was held on November 26 to find out whether there is an increase in reading and the results of the post-test II of the researcher show an increase. Based on the findings above in implementing the RARE strategy in class, the data collected through the test as described in the previous findings section shows that the RARE strategy is effective on reading comprehension students at SMP Labuhan Deli. The average score increased significantly after the second cycle posttest using the RARE strategy.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis in the previous chapter, the following conclusions are the RARE strategy can improve students' reading skills as indicated the score they get. Furthermore, from student responses to teaching and learning activities during PTK. It can be concluded that students like the RARE strategy. This is evidenced by their participation in answering questions from the teacher, discussions, and their pronunciation in reading and their confidence in reading. Students are more active and participate in the process of teaching and learning to read. Therefore, the RARE strategy can be an alternative strategy for teachers in teaching reading which can improve and maintain their reading skills. In the first test (pretest) students passed KKM 75 as many as 2 students out of 30 students (6.6%). In the second test (posttest 1) there were 16 out of 30 students (53.3%) who got an increase in grades of 75 or passed the KKM. In the third test (posttest II) there were 27 out of 30 students who passed KKM 75 (90%).

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